

Demographics

Gender

As can be seen in Figure 1, a significant majority of respondents are male, with a smaller proportion of female participants and an even smaller or non-visible representation of non-binary or other genders. We recognize that the gender imbalance could introduce biases toward male-centric viewpoints in software development communication practices. This limits understanding of how diverse gender groups might perceive or utilize different communication channels, potentially overlooking gender-specific preferences or challenges. Although, the selection of GitHub contributors to be invited for the survey was completely random, we plan on taking proactive steps in future studies to balance this breakdown and get more insights from non-male identifying respondents.

Figure 1: Gender breakdown the respondents

Geographic Area

Figures 2 and 3 show a distribution that indicates a strong Western bias, particularly from North America and Western Europe. Insights and preferences revealed in the survey may predominantly reflect the communication practices and technological adoption common in these regions, potentially limiting the applicability of findings to other global contexts where software development environments might differ.

To enhance the diversity and representativeness of survey responses in global studies, implementing multilingual surveys and targeted recruitment strategies are essential. Conducting surveys in multiple languages is crucial to overcome language barriers that might prevent non-English speakers from participating. Beyond mere translation, it's important to culturally localize the survey content, ensuring that questions are relevant and sensitive to cultural nuances. To address the underrepresentation of certain regions, targeted recruitment efforts are necessary. This can be achieved by collaborating with local universities, technology communities, and industry groups within these regions.

Figure 2: Map showing geographic areas of the respondents - darker colours indicate higher number of respondents

Figure 3: Country breakdown of the respondents

Age

Figure 4 shows that a distribution that indicates a strong representation of young to mid-career professionals, who likely have a good mix of fresh perspectives and moderate industry experience. This demographic may be adept with current technologies and communication tools, influencing the survey results towards these tools' effectiveness and integration in daily operations.

Figure 4: Age groups of the respondents

Software Development Experience

A significant portion of respondents rated their experience 10+ years, indicating a substantial representation of highly experienced developers. Despite the young age profile, the high experience rating suggests that many respondents consider themselves highly skilled or knowledgeable, which could reflect confidence in using various communication channels or familiarity with diverse development environments.

Figure 5: Age categories of the respondents

Role in Associated GitHub Project

The dominance of active contributors and maintainers suggests that the survey sample is heavily composed of individuals deeply involved in project development and management, as seen on Figure 6. This could influence the survey results towards preferences and practices that favor active development roles, possibly overlooking the needs and perspectives of more peripheral or less frequent contributors.

Figure 6: Age categories of the respondents